

DELAMINATIONS AND ULTRASOUND ASSISTED REPAIR OF BALLISTICALLY LOADED GFRP

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ABSTRACT

To determine the types of plate damages made of GFRP they were subjected by shooting on the specially developed accelerating setup. Approximation of experimental data was got the value of the ballistic limit - about 180 meters per second. The largest area of damage is formed near the ballistic limit. This is due to the fact that at these speed, the sample absorbs the kinetic energy of the impactor by the delamination. It was found that at the impact point the interlayer crack gaps (delamination thickness) reaches ~50 microns. The effective method of delamination repair was developed with use of a liquid matrix compound and an ultrasound exciter to help the heating of viscous matrix up and fill into gaps (crack and delaminations) through the small diameter holes, preliminary drilled in the area of delamination. There were studied the factors influenced on the rheological properties of the matrix (epoxy compound viscosity and surface tension in terms of capillary effects). It was shown that a matrix vibro heating up to the temperature of 60 °C allows completely fill the above-mentioned crack of delamination at the length up to 20 mm for 1.5 minute. Further, for complete matrix curing we used the local infrared heater. As a result, after the repair, GFRP strength properties increased up to 80-90% of pristine one.

1 INTRODUCTION

There are two cases of defect formation when the composite structures are used, for example, in aviation: ground operations and flight accidental damages. Low velocity impact causes at falling debris or tools impact with relatively low initial heights during ground operations. High velocity impact (bullets or fragments from exploding munitions, concrete debris from under the front wheel during take-off) causes at flight accidents. Large damages are found upon inspection during ground operations and then structural repairs are conducted. Consequences of falling debris or hail impacts could be invisible but reduction of structural strength could be significant [1].

Bullet perforates all layers of the laminate composites upon impact and forms rounded shape holes during high velocity impact. However, in case of low velocity impact, the main result is delamination [1-3]. Delamination area could be significant and reduces residual strength substantially [4-6]. Hence, delamination needs to be repaired. The different methods were developed to repair damaged area by using external and internal patches. Effectiveness of this methods was studied experimentally [7] and numerically with help of a finite element analysis [8].

There are three another types of repairs along with the bonded repair. They are fill, injection and bolted repairs [9]. Fill repairs are conducted through applied epoxy resins onto the damaged area for

such non-structural damage as minor scratches, gouges, nicks, and dings. Injection repair uses low-viscosity compounds that are injected into composite delaminations [10, 11]. Bolted repairs (when patch is attached to the structure by using bolts) are usually done on thick, highly loaded composite laminates [12]. This method of repair is irrational because the thickness and weight of structure are increased and it has a high labour-intensive process.

Therefore, injection repairs are used for the small damages caused only delamination. This method of repair is operative, non-destructive and can be applied for structures with any size and shape.

The basis of this method is filling of voids and cracks inside delaminated composites after low velocity impact and bonding damage layers with the injected compound. Sometimes compound was reinforced by nanoparticles for increase strength properties. Several evenly spaced small-diameter holes are drilled for better compound filling. Two or more holes are generally required; one hole is used to inject the compound and the others acting as a vent. Compound is injected under low or moderate pressure to help the compound flow into a tight delamination.

Thunga et al. [10] injected the repair resin with a small amount of liquid phase organometallic-based catalyst to bisphenol E cyanate ester. Before the repair, the injection hole was drilled in the centre of the delaminated area with six evenly spaced vent holes placed just on the edge of the delaminated area.

As noticed in work [11], drilling of the holes can possibly make the additional damage and some experience must be needed for this operation. Also, it is difficult to estimate how successful the repair has been without post-repair testing and sophisticated NDT.

To successful injection repair of delaminations and cracks with width of tens of micrometres, the compound would necessary exhibit both low viscosity and good wettability with the composite surface. Apparently, that small cracks can be considered as 'capillaries' because phenomena arising in cracks can be considered as 'a capillary phenomena'.

Despite of the significant amount publications of repair, there are no summarizing recommendations for repair of damages after barely visible impact (BVI). In previous work [13] it was suggested to use the infrared camera for detection of delamination area and the cheap method of repair in delaminated composites after BVI. This method is based on the use of ultrasound device (frequency ~18 kHz, power 600 W) for heating compound. In operation, the exciter heats the resin, increases its fluidity, thereby improving the impregnation of resin into the zone of the delamination by the action of surface wetting.

However, these investigations did not consider a number of factors such as size of delamination area, rheological properties of the compound (epoxy-phenolic compound viscosity and surface tension in terms of capillary effects), etc. Here we can add that these parameters are the functions of temperature and should be determined experimentally. In this paper, we will focus on investigation of the rheological properties of the near-room-temperature repair compound - epoxy resin ED-20 and amine-type hardener polyethylene-polyamine (PEPA), 100:10 (by mass).

2 BALLISTIC TESTS

The GFRP plates made of STEF (matrix – epoxy resin, filler - plain weave glass fibre fabric, six layers, 2 mm of thickness) were fired at the stand [14] for study failure mechanisms upon ballistic impact. Special powder gun stand for acceleration of projectiles (steel spherical impactors, 6.35 mm diameter, weight of 1.05 g) with terminal velocity 50-900 m/s by using standard dowel hammering cartridge was developed. Experimental data was then fitted by least-square regression according to the classical Lambert-Jonas equation (Fig. 1). According to these data, the perforation begins with velocity ~180 m/s (ballistic limit V_{50}).

Figure 1: Lambert-Jonas fit with actual tests measurements for residual velocity vs. initial velocity.

3 DELAMINATION AREA

To determine the delamination areas all fired plates were observed. The dependence of delamination area vs. initial velocity V_0 was obtained as results of experimental data processing (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: The dependence of the area of delaminations as the function of impactor initial velocity.

As you can see the maximum delamination area forms when the velocity is close to ballistic limit. Main reason of it is that the specimens absorb the all kinetic energy of impactor at this velocity. There were observed from one to three surfaces of the delamination (Fig. 3). The first was relatively small and forms at the striking side with tear front ply supposedly. The second area has the largest area and locates near the midplane. The third one is situated at the backside of specimen. Thus, to have the information about crack size specimens were cut using low-speed diamond saw and than they were investigate using digital microscope. At the Figure 3, cross-sectional micrograph was shown. It was found that at the impact point the interlayer crack gaps (delamination thickness) reaches ~50 microns.

Figure 3: Delaminations and crack gap.

4 RESIDUAL STRENGTH

The tests provided on tensile specimens with ballistic damages were performed at INSTRON testing machine to determine the residual strength with such defects. The strain was measured by using Dynamic Strain Gauge Extensometer 2630-107.

According to experimental results the residual strength vs. delamination area and initial velocity were plotted (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: The dependence of residual strength vs. delamination area (left) and initial velocity (right).

As it follows from Figure 4, firstly sharp reducing of GFRP strength properties occurs when the velocity increases. Then we have near constant value of residual strength. It maybe explains that perforation of the sample occurs due to fibre breakage with minimum delamination area when velocity is above 300 m/s. The reducing of strength due to fibre breakage is more than due to delamination.

As the result for GFRP specimens made of STEF (thickness ~1.9mm, width of 40mm) residual strength under tension decreases from 380 to 210 MPa according to initial velocity and delamination area. It means that taking safety factor equal 2.0 we would not see the rupture of structure under the

single loading. It corresponds with reducing of strength for composite samples with open hole, Daniels [15]. Thus, residual strength of perforated GFRP could be determined using the express-method based on the specific failure energy and open-hole scheme with known equivalent diameter of the hole as the function of delaminated area [16].

5 REPAIR

Because small damages reduce significantly the fracture load of specimens, there was developed the effective method of repair of delamination. We used cold curing liquid matrix compound and ultrasound exciter to help the heating of viscous matrix and fill it into gaps (crack and delaminations) through the small diameter holes, preliminary drilled in the area of delamination.

The viscosity, surface tension and wettability on the composite surface are the important factors influencing on the speed and time of impregnation of delamination and on the maximum possible repaired size of delamination area. In addition, polymerization time of compound was considered and related with this viscosity changing.

5.1 Surface effects (contact angle, surface tension) and viscosity

Contact angle

Wetting of the solid surface is characterized by the contact angle θ . Experiments to determine how the contact angle changes vs. temperature of compound using method of sessile drop were carried out. The method of sessile drop provides a measure of the angle between solid and liquid surface at the contact point of the three phases. Smooth glass plate was taken to substitute relatively rough GFRP surface in our experiments. The result of dependence of contact angle vs. temperature is shown in Figure 5.

Surface tension

The experiments for surface tension σ were carried out using method of Wilhelmy plate [17] for variety temperatures of compound. In this method, the glass plate interacts with the liquid surface. In this case liquid wets the plate along of plate perimeter.

The surface tension was calculated according to measured force F , wetting length L (perimeter of plate) and contact angle θ obtained previously:

$$\sigma = \frac{F}{L \cdot \cos \theta} \quad (1)$$

The dependence of surface tension vs. temperature is almost linear for far from the critical (boiling) temperature. Therefore obtained results were approximated of the straight line (Fig. 5).

Critical lifting height

The maximum lifting height of the compound for variety temperatures was calculated using the equation [17]:

$$l_{\max} = \frac{2 \cdot \sigma \cdot \cos \theta}{\rho \cdot g \cdot d} \quad (2)$$

where g is the acceleration of gravity, ρ is the density of the liquid, l_{\max} is the lifting height of liquid in the capillary and d is delamination thickness equal in this work ~50 microns.

Viscosity of compound and curing time

Experimental investigation of viscosity of compound for variety temperatures was conducted on the viscometer Brookfield CAP 2000+. As the result, dependence of compound viscosity vs. temperature was obtained (Fig. 5).

Figure 5: The dependences of contact angle, viscosity and surface tension vs. temperature.

According to Figure 5, viscosity of compound sharply decreases and thus impregnation rate of cracks is increased. However, the curing time of compound is reduced for high temperature. Therefore, experiments to determine how the viscosity of compound changes vs. the time were carried out for variety temperatures. Experimental data are shown on Figure 6.

Figure 6: The dependence of viscosity of compound vs. curing time.

5.2 Results

The dependence of viscosity vs. time (during polymerisation) at any temperature within the range from 24 to 90 °C was obtained through of approximation of the experimental results. Then the

asymptotic function of impregnation time vs. length of liquid-filled capillary was founded (Fig.7) by using equation of impregnation speed of capillary [17]:

$$\frac{dl}{dt} = \frac{r^2 \cdot \rho \cdot g}{8 \cdot \eta(t) \cdot l} \cdot (l_{max} - l) \quad (3)$$

where $\eta(t)$ is the function of viscosity vs. time; r is radius of capillary equal of delamination thickness; l_{max} is the lifting height of liquid in the capillary; l is length of liquid-filled capillary at a time t .

Figure 7: The dependence of impregnation time vs. length of liquid-filled capillary.

It was found experimentally that ultrasound exciter used in this method of repair able to heat of viscous matrix to temperature 55...60 °C. Therefore, we compared the rheological parameters for three different temperatures. Results of this comparison are shown in Table 1.

T (°C)	θ (deg.)	σ (mN/m)	$\eta(t)$ (Pa·s)	l_{max} (mm)	t_{max} (s)	l (mm)
60	12.37	95	$0.386e^{0.0058x}$	325	400	29.75
50	17.70	102	$0.915e^{0.0036x}$	344	400	23.25
40	23.92	112	$4.196e^{0.0019x}$	362	400	12.95

Table 1: The parameters of epoxy compound.

These results indicated that maximum impregnation effect was achieved at a temperature of 60 °C. This temperature is optimal temperature of compound used to repair cracks and delaminations in proposed method.

Then to get full polymerization local infrared heater with power of 300 W was used. This device could heat the composite surface up to 150 °C by focusing beams of light. As a result, after the repair, GFRP compressive and tensile strength increases up to 80-90% of pristine.

6 CONCLUSIONS

On the base of provided experiments and calculations, we can say that the full repair of delamination is possible with known rheological and physical characteristics of uncured resin and geometry of delamination to estimate capillary effects for healing of damaged composite.

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